

The MAMA-SYNTH Challenge: Synthesizing Virtual Contrast-Enhancement in Breast MRI: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

The MAMA-SYNTH Challenge: Synthesizing Virtual Contrast-Enhancement in Breast MRI

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

MAMA-SYNTH

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) is a key modality for breast cancer detection, characterization, and treatment monitoring, but its reliance on gadolinium-based contrast agents introduces safety concerns, contraindications, increased cost, and clinical workflow burden. Recent advances in deep generative modeling have demonstrated the feasibility of synthesizing post-contrast breast MRI from pre-contrast acquisitions, enabling virtual contrast-enhanced imaging as a potential alternative or complement to conventional DCE-MRI.

From a technical perspective, progress in this area has been rapid but fragmented, with studies relying on heterogeneous datasets, inconsistent evaluation protocols, and limited clinical validation. This challenge addresses these limitations by providing a standardized, clinically grounded benchmark for pre-contrast to contrast-enhanced breast MRI synthesis. By jointly evaluating image fidelity, lesion-specific realism, distributional consistency, and downstream clinical utility, the challenge aims to advance trustworthy synthetic imaging methods and support future translation toward contrast-reduced or contrast-free breast MRI protocols.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Contrast Agent, Synthesis, DCE-MRI, Generative Models, Breast Cancer

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge introduces a breast-MRI-specific benchmark for pre-contrast to single timepoint post-contrast synthesis that explicitly integrates lesion-focused image evaluation, radiomics-based distributional assessment, and downstream clinical tasks within a single standardized framework. While modality and contrast synthesis challenges have been explored in other domains (e.g., brain MRI), to our knowledge this is the first dedicated challenge focusing on virtual contrast generation in breast DCE-MRI and furthermore introduces a novel multi-dimensional evaluation framework aligned to clinically meaningful endpoints such as tumor segmentation, biomarker variability, and molecular subtype classification. The transparent, rank-based multi-metric evaluation and the use of fixed, pre-trained clinical downstream evaluation models, provide a reproducible and extensible foundation for future benchmarking and regulatory-aligned assessment.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The task of the challenge is to synthesize single-timepoint 2-dimensional post-contrast breast DCE-MRI slices from corresponding pre-contrast T1-weighted MRI inputs using paired clinical data. Participating algorithms operate on pre-contrast images and generate synthetic post-contrast outputs that are evaluated against real acquisitions.

Evaluation reflects both technical and clinical relevance, including whole-image and lesion-focused image fidelity, radiomics-based distributional similarity between real and synthetic domains, and performance on downstream tasks using pre-trained tumor segmentation and breast cancer subtype classification models trained on real DCE-MRI images, but applied to synthesized test images during evaluation.

The challenge targets application scenarios such as contrast-reduced or contrast-free breast MRI, protocol acceleration, and improved accessibility of breast MRI for patients with contraindications to gadolinium-based agents. More broadly, it aims to establish best practices for evaluating synthetic medical images in settings where clinical decision-making depends on subtle, biologically meaningful image features, relevant both in treatment planning and monitoring as well as mass detection, localization, and characterization in the breast MRI domains.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The MAMA-SYNTH Challenge will be hosted as part of the Deep-Breath 2026 Workshop (3rd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care). This workshop emphasizes the integration of AI and imaging to address diagnostic and therapeutic challenges in breast care. For further details, visit the workshop website: <https://deep-breath-miccai.github.io/deepbreath-2026/>

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

This challenge builds upon the established MAMA umbrella for breast cancer challenges, which successfully hosted the MAMA-MIA Challenge last year at MICCAI 2025 [19]. The MAMA-MIA Challenge attracted 86 registered teams, of which 26 teams submitted final results, demonstrating strong engagement and follow-through from the community.

Leveraging this existing network and visibility, and focusing on the timely and relevant topic of contrast synthesis in breast MRI, recently becoming an attainable objective due to advances in deep generative models, we anticipate a comparable level of interest. Based on participation trends from the previous challenge and the more specialized scope of the current topic, we estimate participation from approximately 15-25 teams.

Outreach will primarily target research groups and institutions that participated in previous MAMA challenges, as well as new teams working in medical imaging, breast MRI, and generative modeling.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Upon completion of the MAMA-SYNTH Challenge, we intend to publish a comprehensive summary of the challenge outcomes, including key analyses and insights. The publication will be developed collaboratively with the challenge organizers, clinical and technical collaborators, and the top-performing teams, each invited to contribute first and last authorship. The manuscript will present a detailed, multi-dimensional evaluation of the generative models, with analyses stratified by institution and clinically relevant variables.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be conducted primarily online using the Grand Challenge platform, with which we are already in contact and for which the corresponding application is currently being prepared. The platform will support challenge hosting, data distribution, submission handling, and evaluation.

In addition, results and outcomes will be presented during the conference using standard presentation infrastructure. No specialized equipment is required; a projector, microphones, and standard audiovisual facilities will be sufficient.

TASK 1: Synthesizing Virtual Contrast-Enhancement in Breast MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) is a key modality for breast cancer detection, characterization, and treatment monitoring, but its reliance on gadolinium-based contrast agents introduces safety concerns, contraindications, increased cost, and clinical workflow burden. Recent advances in deep generative modeling have demonstrated the feasibility of synthesizing post-contrast breast MRI from pre-contrast acquisitions, enabling virtual contrast-enhanced imaging as a potential alternative or complement to conventional DCE-MRI.

From a technical perspective, progress in this area has been rapid but fragmented, with studies relying on heterogeneous datasets, inconsistent evaluation protocols, and limited clinical validation. This challenge addresses these limitations by providing a standardized, clinically grounded benchmark for pre-contrast to contrast-enhanced breast MRI synthesis. By jointly evaluating image fidelity, lesion-specific realism, distributional consistency, and downstream clinical utility, the challenge aims to advance trustworthy synthetic imaging methods and support future translation toward contrast-reduced or contrast-free breast MRI protocols.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Contrast Agent, Synthesis, DCE-MRI, Generative Models, Breast Cancer

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Organizing Committee:

Richard Osuala*(1), Smriti Joshi*(1), Jarek van Dijk*(2), Luyi Han (2), Lidia Garrucho (1), Maria Laura Cosaka (4), Antonio Portaluri (6), Oliver Diaz (1, 3)

*challenge co-leads

Advisory Committee:

Yaofei Duan (2), Tianyu Zhang (2), Ritse Mann (2), Daniel Mysler (4), Karim Lekadir (1, 5), Simone Balocco (1)

(1) Departament de Matemàtiques i Informàtica, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

- (2) Radboud University Medical Centre, The Netherlands
- (3) Computer Vision Center, Bellaterra, Spain
- (4) Instituto Alexander Fleming, Argentina
- (5) Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), Barcelona, Spain
- (6) The Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Smriti Joshi (Smriti.Joshi@ub.edu)

Richard Osuala (Richard.Osuala@gmail.com)

Jarek van Dijk (Jarek.vanDijk@radboudumc.nl)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, Maria Laura Cosaka and Daniel Mysler are radiologists. Roles: Creation and provision of annotated breast MRI datasets, revision of annotations, clinical interpretation and value assessment.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

Deep-Breath Workshop at MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.ub.edu/mama-synth/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Participants may modify the training dataset through cleaning, augmentation, resampling training distribution, preprocessing, or integration of additional publicly available data.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Publicly available data is allowed but private annotations of such data is prohibited.

We note that participants are allowed to train their models on any further dataset, as long as said dataset is publicly available. To ensure fair evaluation across participating teams, the usage of private data is not allowed in this challenge. We further note that by participating in this challenge, participants agree to comply with EO 14117, 28 CFR Part 202, and Guide Notice NOT-OD-25-083 and acknowledge that the usage of NIH Controlled-access Data Repositories (CADRs) is prohibited in this challenge.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

To recognize outstanding contributions and encourage high-quality participation, the challenge will offer the following awards:

Challenge Awards:

1st Position - €500

2nd Position - €250

3rd Position - €150

Awarded to the top-ranked teams based on the official challenge evaluation criteria, recognizing overall excellence in performance.

Best Paper Award: €300

Awarded to the team whose challenge paper demonstrates exceptional scientific quality, with particular emphasis on methodological novelty. This award highlights innovative approaches, originality of the proposed methods, and potential impact on the field, independent of leaderboard ranking. The papers submitted to the Deep Breath Workshop will be considered for this award.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Results for the top 3 performing teams will be announced in the month of August through the Grand Challenge platform.

The respective rankings will be announced during the Deep-Breath Workshop at MICCAI 2026. Following the announcement of the results, the leaderboard will be published online with the respective performance metrics.

If a participating team requests their identity to remain hidden, the anonymized results will be displayed in the final leaderboard.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

A journal paper describing the challenge will be submitted listing the top-performing methods. First and Last Author of the short paper, submitted to the Deep-Breath Workshop 2026, qualify as authors for the joint publication. Participants are free to publish their results separately, but can only mention overall results once the challenge paper is published (submission to arXiv is considered as a sufficient waiting period).

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Grand Challenge (<https://mamasynth.grand-challenge.org/>). Participants will also have to submit a technical report describing their method and results describing the model submitted in the test phase.

Participants are permitted to use only the provided training data and publicly available resources, including datasets and/or pre-trained models that are accessible without restriction and licensed under CC-BY-NC-SA or equivalent or more permissive licenses.

The use of manual or semi-automatic annotation mechanisms, i.e., annotations that cannot be reproduced automatically, is strictly prohibited in valid submissions.

All participants must explicitly declare any publicly available datasets and/or pre-trained models used for training in the technical report.

The use of any non-publicly available datasets or pre-trained models is not permitted under any circumstances.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The challenge will run in two phases: validation and test. During the validation phase, teams can submit a maximum of 4 times evaluating their proposed method on a set of 50 images. Successful submission to the validation phase will be a requirement for the final submission in the test phase, which will be limited to one submission and should be complemented with a technical report detailing the methodology.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release date of the training cases: not applicable as the training data is already public.

Validation Phase: May 1, 2026

Test Phase: June 15, 2026

Last submission: June 30, 2026

Results Release: August 1, 2026 (Challenge winners will be contacted to invite them to MICCAI 2026)

Associated workshop days: October 4 & October 8, 2026

Winners announcement during the Deep-Breath workshop at MICCAI 2026.

All phases close at 23:59h of the day indicated (CEST time zone).

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The MAMA-SYNTH Challenge includes data contributed by multiple clinical centers for testing and validation purposes. Ethical approval for the use of data from the Instituto Alexander Fleming, Argentina has been fully granted; Informed consent was obtained from all subjects at their respective institutions, and the protocol for using the data was approved by the institutional review board. For Radboud University Medical Centre, the ethics review process is currently underway, with positive preliminary feedback obtained.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial). This applies to the training data only, while the validation and testing data will remain private.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Code and scoring/evaluation formulas for the MAMA-SYNTH challenge will be made available in the MAMA-SYNTH GitHub repository: <https://github.com/mama-research/mama-synth>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participant code is encouraged to be open-access, but this is not a strict exclusion criteria. Particularly, code submission is mandatory for top-3 ranked teams as a condition for being awarded the challenge awards and co-authorship in the joint publication. The code must include training scripts, inference scripts, and documentation of external data/pretrained models used, in order for the challenge committee to reproduce and revise the submission and obtained results.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This project has received funding from the projects AIMED (Grant No. PID2023-146786OB-I00) and FUTURE-ES (Grant No. PID2021-126724OB-I00) from the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities of Spain. Also, this work was partially supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreements No. 101057699 (RadioVal) and No. 101057091 (ODELIA).

No other conflicts of interest.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification,Segmentation,Prediction,Image Synthesis

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics

defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Diagnostic MRI with malignant cancers, spanning multiple centers, vendors, imaging protocols, molecular subtypes, and risk groups (BRCA1, BRCA2).

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of patients with advanced breast cancer that underwent neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC) in their treatment planning.

Key inclusion criteria for this task include:

1. Histologically confirmed diagnosis of breast cancer.
2. Availability of pre-treatment DCE-MRI scans.
3. Tumours localized to one breast with clearly visible primary tumour regions.

Exclusion criteria may include prior breast surgery, incomplete DCE-MRI sequences, or scans of insufficient quality.

This cohort is representative of patients for whom accurate tumour segmentation is crucial for treatment planning, including surgical guidance and response assessment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The challenge is based on dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) of the breast, including pre-contrast and post-contrast T1-weighted image volumes acquired as part of standard clinical breast MRI protocols.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

N/A - only the t1-weighted fat-saturated pre-contrast images are provided to the participants.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A - only the t1-weighted fat-saturated pre-contrast images are provided to the participants.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The image data represent the breast and adjacent chest wall region acquired using dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI). The data include pre-contrast and post-contrast T1-weighted images

routinely acquired in clinical breast MRI protocols.

The challenge cohort is derived from retrospective, multi-institutional clinical datasets and reflects variability in scanners, acquisition protocols, and patient populations encountered in real-world clinical practice. The target entity in the final biomedical application is the same as in the challenge cohort, namely the breast and chest region imaged with DCE-MRI for the assessment of breast cancer.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participating algorithms are designed to target image structures that demonstrate uptake of contrast agent, with primary emphasis on malignant breast lesions. These lesions are confirmed through histopathological examination and serve as the clinically relevant structures of interest.

While algorithms operate on full breast DCE-MRI volumes, evaluation focuses specifically on the accurate synthesis and preservation of tumor-related enhancement patterns, including lesion conspicuity and contrast uptake characteristics that are relevant for diagnosis, segmentation, and subtype characterization. No distinction is made between target and challenge cohorts in terms of algorithmic focus.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

The goal is to identify algorithms that can synthesize post-contrast breast DCE-MRI images from pre-contrast inputs while preserving clinically relevant information. In particular, the challenge evaluates the ability of methods to accurately reproduce tumor contrast uptake patterns, maintain lesion delineability for downstream segmentation, retain biologically meaningful imaging cues relevant to breast cancer subtype characterization, and generate globally realistic images that are consistent with real post-contrast DCE-MRI data. Participants submit only image synthesis models that generate post-contrast breast DCE-MRI images from pre-contrast inputs. Classification (CLF) and segmentation (SEG) are not participant tasks; all downstream evaluations (CLF, SEG) are performed using fixed, pre-trained models maintained by the organizers. This ensures fair comparison and assesses whether synthesized images preserve clinically relevant diagnostic information.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The imaging modality for the challenge includes pre-treatment DCE-MRI scans, which are among the most sensitive imaging techniques for evaluating breast cancer and guiding treatment planning. The datasets include pre-contrast and at least two post-contrast images on each DCE-MRI sequence. The training set is the publicly available MAMA-MIA dataset [1] consisting 1506 patients, explained in detail in the following sections. The testing and validation datasets are private and are acquired in two centers:

Radboud University Medical centre, located in the Netherlands

200 pre-contrast and 200 post-contrast DCE-MRI scans.

General acquisition details:

- Plane: Axial (99.5%), Unspecified(0.5%)
- Magnetic Field Strength: 3T (100%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (100.0%), No (0.0%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (100%)
- Acquisition protocols: t1_fl3d_tra_Dixon_W (100%).
- Contrast agents: DOTAREM (99.0%), GADOVIST (0.5%), Unspecified (0.5%).

Instituto Alexander Fleming, located in Argentina

100 pre-contrast and 100 post-contrast DCE-MRI scans.

General acquisition details:

- Plane: Axial.
- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T
- Fat suppression: Yes. (FAT, FAT Classic, Special, Water)
- Scanner Manufacturer: GE
- Contrast Agents: DOTAREM, GADOVIST

Additional details about the validation and testing datasets will be added to the MAMA-SYNTH challenge webpage (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-synth/>).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Train Dataset:

The training dataset cohort is built from four public collections available on The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). Namely, level 2b cohort from I-SPY1/ACRIN 6657 trial (I-SPY1) [9], I-SPY2/ACRIN 6689 trial [6, 7], NACT-Pilot [8], and Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI [2]. The training dataset was annotated by experts for this challenge and is publicly available and hosted on the MAMA-MIA Synapse repository [5] (<https://doi.org/10.7303/syn60868042>). The annotation protocol for the training dataset is described in the MAMA-MIA Dataset publication [1].

General acquisition details:

- Acquisition Plane: Axial (84.4%), Sagittal (15.6%)
- Magnetic Field Strength: 1.5T (72.1%), 3T (27.9%)
- Fat Suppression: Yes (99.6%), No (0.4%)
- Scanner Manufacturers: Siemens (27,3%), GE (64,1%), Philips: (8,6%)

Validation and Test Dataset:

Radboud University Medical Centre, located in the Netherlands

For acquisition, a T1-weighted 3D fast low-angle shot (FL3D2) gradient-echo MRI sequence was used in the transverse plane, Dixon water-only reconstruction (100%), providing high-resolution isotropic volumetric imaging (TR ~5–10 ms, TE ~2–5 ms, flip angle 8–15°, slice thickness ~1 mm)

- Image dimensions: 416×416 pixels (100.0%)
- Pixel spacing in both X and Y dimensions lies in the range of 0.8654 to 0.9615 mm, with a mean of 0.8689, median of 0.8654mm and standard deviation of: 0.0157mm.
- Slice thickness: 1.0 mm (65.7%), 1.1 mm (23%), 1.2 mm (9.0%), 1.3 mm (1.5%), 1.4 mm (1.0%).

Instituto Alexander Fleming, located in Argentina

For image acquisition, a dynamic contrast-enhanced (DCE) breast MRI was performed in the axial plane using spectral fat suppression. A 3D volumetric sequence was obtained with an in-plane spatial resolution of 0.8×0.8 mm (TR 4.2 ms, TE 2 ms, flip angle 12°) and a slice thickness of 1.1 mm. The image matrix was 512×512 , corresponding to a pixel spacing of 0.875 mm.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training dataset comprises 1,506 cases from four collections: ISPY1[9] (171 cases, 1 U.S. center), ISPY2 [6, 7] (980 cases, 22 U.S. centers), NACT [8] (64 cases, 1 U.S. center), and DUKE [2] (291 cases, 1 U.S. center), all sourced from TCIA.

Validation and test datasets were obtained from two distinct institutions, Radboud University Medical Centre in The Netherlands (200 cases) and Instituto Alexander Fleming in Argentina (100 cases), capturing institutional and geographical diversity.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The patients were diagnosed with biopsy-confirmed breast cancer.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In this challenge, each case corresponds to a single patient. The training dataset, MAMA-MIA [1], contains extensive information, including clinical and patient data, DCE-MRI scans including the pre-contrast and at least two post-contrast phases, and 3D manual segmentation masks of the primary tumor. For validation, participants are provided only with the 2D pre-contrast slice, which will be evaluated against the corresponding post-contrast peak enhancement phase, both at the full-image level and within the tumor ROI.

Additional details about the datasets will be added to the MAMA-SYNTH challenge webpage (<https://www.ub.edu/mama-synth/dataset>).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The challenge dataset consists of pre-contrast and post-contrast phases of Breast DCE-MRI. The size of evaluation sets will be as follows:

- Validation Set: 50 cases.
- Testing Set: 300 cases

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

No explicit labels are required for network training. However, the evaluation framework includes ROI-based analyses, where the ROI corresponds to the primary tumor segmentation provided with the training data (i.e., the MAMA-MIA dataset [1]).

For the test and validation sets, all cases from Instituto Alexander Fleming, Argentina are fully annotated, while the cases from Radboud University Medical Centre, the Netherlands, are currently undergoing radiologist-led quality checks.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset proportions were chosen to ensure a balanced distribution of cases while maintaining adequate representation of molecular subtypes and risk groups across all splits. The training set includes 1,506 cases sourced from TCIA. The validation set comprises 50 cases, carefully stratified by tumor subtype and hospital of origin to ensure balanced representation. Its smaller size is intentional, enabling participants to perform multiple evaluations efficiently within the available GPU resources. The final test set consists of 300 cases from two hospitals in the Netherlands and Argentina, capturing diverse geographical and clinical variability, while enabling evaluation of generalizability along with model performance.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Train Dataset:

Detailed class distributions are reported in the MAMA-MIA dataset paper [1]. Overall, the dataset is well-balanced by age, with 314 patients (21%) under 40 and half under 50 at diagnosis. Ethnicity reflects U.S. demographics: 16% African American, <6% Asian, 2.3% other, and 74.9% Caucasian. Tumor subtypes include 49.6% luminal A/B, 11.2% HER2-enriched, 2.3% HER2-pure, and 33.1% triple-negative.

Validation and Test Datasets:

Radboud University Medical centre, located in the Netherlands:

- Malignancy distribution: Of the included studies, 200 cases (100%) were biopsy-confirmed malignancies
- Patient age: The mean patient age was 57.6 years (median 58.5 years), ranging from 26 to 85 years, with a standard deviation of 12.3 years.

Instituto Alexander Fleming, located in Argentina:

- Malignancy distribution: Of the included studies, 100 cases (100%) were biopsy-confirmed malignancies
- Patient age: The mean patient was 46.3 years (median 45 years), ranging from 27 to 82 years, with a standard deviation of 11.4 years.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

A total of 300 DCE-MRI cases from two centers have been newly acquired for the validation and testing of the proposed algorithms in the MAMA-SYNTH Challenge. This inclusion ensures a robust evaluation of algorithm performance on diverse, real-world imaging data that has not been previously accessible, further enhancing the challenge's impact and generalizability. The test sets represent intentionally unseen domains for external validation to allow drawing clinically-meaningful conclusions from center-stratified performance metrics, per-center robustness analysis in post-hoc evaluation, guided by quantified domain shift between centers based on distribution comparison metrics (e.g. FRD).

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The use case is image-to-image translation; therefore, no explicit labels are required for network training. However, the evaluation framework includes ROI-based analyses. For this purpose, primary tumors were segmented in the validation and test datasets. The primary tumour was manually segmented in the first post-contrast DCE-MRI image. This was done either directly or a baseline nnUNet was used to provide initial automatic segmentation of the primary tumour, which were then corrected by an expert clinician.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Training Dataset:

The tumour annotations were done in NiftI format in the first post-contrast phase using as reference the subtraction image (first post-contrast minus pre-contrast phases) if needed. All the annotation protocol details are thoroughly explained in the MAMA-MIA dataset publication [1].

Validation and Test Datasets:

Annotators were instructed to verify and perform tumor segmentations on post-contrast and subtraction sequences (i.e. post-contrast minus pre-contrast, approximately 90 seconds after contrast injection). Both mass and non-mass enhancements were annotated, with mass enhancements outlined as precisely as possible and non-mass enhancements annotated coarsely.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The Training Dataset was annotated by a group of 18 experts (16 radiologists and 2 expert clinicians) with an average of 10 years of experience in breast cancer from 11 different institutions around Europe, Asia, and Africa.

The Validation and Test Datasets were annotated by two board-certified breast cancer radiologists from each participating center.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Following MAMA-MIA dataset conventions [1, 20] as training dataset, general pre-processing was applied for all cases (Training, Validation, and Test Sets), as outlined below.

1) Conversion to NiftI Format:

The raw DICOM files were converted to NiftI format using the pycad library (<https://github.com/amine0110/pycad/tree/main>). This standardization simplifies data handling and ensures compatibility with most computational frameworks.

2) Dataset Harmonization:

- Image Quality Control: Quality checks were performed to exclude scans with significant artifacts or incomplete

sequences.

- Clinical and Imaging Data Extraction: Relevant clinical and imaging metadata were extracted from the DICOM headers and integrated into the dataset for downstream analyses.
- Standardized Naming and Folder Structure: A uniform naming convention and directory organization were applied to all sequences for consistent data access.

3) Image Orientation Standardization:

- Sagittal Images: Reoriented to the PSR (posterior-superior-right) coordinate system. This orientation aligns with standard practices in breast MRI sagittal acquisitions, ensuring consistency.
- Axial Images: Reoriented to the LAS (left-anterior-superior) coordinate system, widely used for standardizing axial breast MRI acquisitions.

These orientation adjustments minimize errors due to rotations, preserve anatomical accuracy, and ensure compatibility with computational models tailored to specific acquisition planes.

No additional preprocessing methods, such as bias field correction, intensity normalization (e.g., z-score or min-max normalization), or voxel resampling, were applied to the dataset. This approach allows participants the flexibility to tailor preprocessing techniques to their specific model requirements, depending on the downstream task. Intensity normalization, bias field correction and other preprocessing and data augmentation techniques are intentionally left to participants to allow methodological flexibility. However, code will be provided adapted to the training dataset to pass the images to the target 16-bit PNG slices (512×512) with z-score normalization applied at the dataset level. Also, the evaluation metrics are computed on standardized normalized intensities. Both evaluation and preprocessing scripts for data conversion and normalization will be made publicly available in our GitHub repository.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The tumor segmentation is performed under a strict protocol and verified by practicing clinicians with multiple years of experience in breast cancer imaging.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The DCE-MRI phases are visually confirmed to be co-registered. Only the biopsy-proven cases are included in the dataset, ensuring a high-quality standard.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The performance of submitted algorithms will be assessed using a combination of image and region-of-interest (ROI) fidelity, and distributional realism as well as downstream task performance metrics. Four metric groups are used, each contributing equally (25%) to the final ranking. While not affecting official ranking, for further insight sensitivity analysis will be performed and reported for transparency, including leave-one-group-out ranking analysis, and ranking variability under alternative weightings (e.g., ROI-prioritized).

(1) Full-Image Image & Distribution Metrics – 25% Computed over the full breast image volume comparing real and synthesized images, compared, as before, using:

1.1 Mean Squared Error (MSE)

1.2 Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) [17]

(2) Tumor ROI Metrics – 25% Computed within a tumor-centered region of interest (tumor mask with a fixed margin) in the real and synthetic images, which are then compared using:

2.1 Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [19]

2.2 Fréchet Radiomics Distance (FRD) [18], computed using a predefined set of radiomic features extracted from synthesized and real peak-enhancement images

(3) Classification (CLF) – 25%

3.1 Binary classification (ROI-based Pre vs. Post): Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC).

3.2 Binary classification (ROI-based Tumor Tissue vs Non-Tumor Tissue): Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AUROC).

Classification is performed using fixed, pre-trained evaluators applied to the synthesized post-contrast (single DCE timepoint) images.

(4) Tumor Segmentation (SEG) – 25%

2D pixel-level Tumor segmentation measured by:

4.1 The Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

4.2 HD95, i.e. the 95th percentile of the Hausdorff Distance.

Segmentation performance is measured by applying a fixed tumor segmentation model to the synthesized images and comparing predicted masks against radiologist-verified ground-truth annotations.

All image-based metrics are computed on intensity-normalized images using a standardized preprocessing

pipeline. FRD will be computed using all radiomic features defined in FRD version 1 based on open-source reproducible code (<https://github.com/RichardObi/frd-score/>) and as defined in the corresponding publication [18], which comprises the IBSI-compliant pyradiomics feature sets: firstorder, GLCM, GLRLM, GLDM, GLSZM, NGTDM.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The proposed metrics are designed to reflect the clinical and technical goals of pre-contrast to post-contrast translation in breast DCE-MRI.

- MSE quantifies pixel-wise fidelity and penalizes large intensity deviations, ensuring preservation of enhancement magnitude.
- LPIPS [17] captures perceptual similarity beyond pixel-wise error and is sensitive to structural and textural differences that can affect lesion appearance.
- Tumor ROI-restricted evaluation emphasizes lesion conspicuity and enhancement realism, which are critical for diagnostic interpretation.
- SSIM [19] within ROI assesses whether synthesized images preserve local structural and textural characteristics, such as intensity patterns and spatial organization, that are critical for accurately representing tumor morphology and contrast enhancement beyond simple pixel-wise similarity.
- Fréchet Radiomics Distance (FRD) [18] measures distributional similarity between synthesized and real images in a radiomics feature space, providing a clinically interpretable assessment of whether synthesized images preserve higher-order imaging biomarkers relevant to breast cancer characterization.
- Pre vs post-contrast ROI-based classification assesses whether synthesized images exhibit the characteristic contrast enhancement patterns within tumor regions, thereby verifying that the generated images capture clinically relevant intensity changes associated with vascularization and lesion activity.
- Contrast enhanced tumor vs non-tumor-containing tissue classification evaluates whether synthesized images preserve tumor-specific texture and enhancement patterns that distinguish malignant from healthy tissue relevant for clinical lesion detection and assessment.
- Dice Similarity Coefficient evaluates whether synthesized images retain sufficient tumor-related information to support automated lesion delineation.

Together, these metrics ensure that algorithms are evaluated not only on visual similarity, but also on clinical utility and biological plausibility.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

For each metric, results are first computed per test case and then averaged across all test cases to obtain a method-level score using the mean per metric.

To preserve interpretable, absolute performance measures, rankings are based on rank aggregation rather than score normalization.

Within each metric, submitted methods are ranked according to their aggregated score (best performance

receives rank 1). For metrics within the same assessment group, ranks are averaged to obtain a group-level rank for each submission. The overall challenge ranking is then determined using Borda-style aggregation, computed as the unweighted average of the four group-level ranks (IMG, ROI, CLF, SEG). The submission with the lowest overall average rank is declared the winner. We emphasize that, raw metric values are not averaged across different units, as we use a hierarchical rank-based aggregation procedure (Borda-style aggregation) exemplified by the following pseudo-code:

RANKING PROCEDURE:

1. For each metric m in metric_group G :
 - a. Compute metric value per test case
 - b. Average metric value across all test cases to get submission score
 - c. Rank all submissions by this metric score

2. For each metric group G (IMG, ROI, CLF, SEG):
 - a. Average the metric-level ranks within G
 - b. This yields a single group-level rank per submission

3. Final ranking:
 - a. Average the 4 group-level ranks
 - b. Rank submissions by this average

If overall average ranks are tied, the ROI group rank is compared first. If still tied, CLF is compared, followed by SEG, and then FULL. If submissions remain tied after all comparisons, multiple winners will be declared.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions are required to provide outputs for all test cases and all metrics.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The proposed ranking scheme was chosen to ensure fair, transparent, and robust comparison across heterogeneous metrics across any number of submissions. Rank-based aggregation avoids sensitivity to metric scale and outliers, which can disproportionately affect normalized score-based methods while depending on submission counts. Publishing separate leaderboards for each assessment group improves transparency and highlights trade-offs between image realism and downstream clinical utility, while the aggregated rank provides a clear and interpretable overall winner.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Aggregating metric values across test cases reduces sensitivity to case-level noise and provides a stable estimate of method performance. Rank-based aggregation further improves robustness by relying on relative ordering rather than absolute metric magnitudes, making the evaluation less sensitive to distributional assumptions and

dataset-specific scaling. This approach is consistent with best practices in comparative algorithm evaluation and is well suited for challenges aiming to inform future regulatory benchmarking.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Performance uncertainty is quantified using nonparametric percentile bootstrap 95% confidence intervals computed by resampling test cases at the patient level with replacement. This approach makes no distributional assumptions and yields confidence intervals for each aggregated metric (mean/median across cases).

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Variability across test cases is reported using the standard deviation and the interquartile range of per-case metric values and visualized using box plots or violin plots; outliers are inspected to characterize common failure modes.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking robustness is assessed via bootstrap resampling of test cases (e.g. recomputing the full ranking per resample) and sensitivity analyses (e.g., leave-one-metric-out). We report the distribution of ranks (median/IQR) and the frequency of achieving top-k positions across resamples.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Pairwise performance differences are assessed post hoc using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests on per-case metric values. Significance analyses are reported for interpretation and do not alter the official rankings.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Submissions must provide outputs for all test cases. Missing outputs for individual cases are assigned the worst observed score for that metric prior to aggregation; submissions missing an entire metric group are excluded from the overall ranking. This policy prevents exploitation of missing values and ensures fair comparison.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All analyses are performed using Python (NumPy, SciPy, pandas, scikit-learn) with reproducible scripts; where applicable, established challenge-analysis tooling (e.g., challengeR) may be used for visualization and robustness analysis.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In addition to the primary evaluation and ranking, the following post hoc analyses will be conducted to better characterize algorithm behavior and challenge outcomes. These analyses are informative only and will not affect

the official rankings, e.g.:

- Inter-algorithm variability: Variability across submitted methods will be analyzed for key metrics (e.g., ROI FRD, Dice, AUROC) to identify which aspects of the task show the greatest disagreement between approaches.

- Error pattern analysis: Qualitative and quantitative analyses will be performed to identify common failure modes, such as inaccurate enhancement in tumor regions, loss of lesion conspicuity, or spurious enhancement in background tissue.

These analyses will be reported in the post-challenge publication to provide additional insights into the strengths, limitations, and open challenges of pre-contrast to post-contrast synthesis in breast DCE-MRI.

While not part of official ranking (to maintain objectivity and reproducibility), we will further include post-hoc clinical assessments. This includes, for instance, structured qualitative lesion realism assessment (lesion conspicuity, enhancement plausibility) alongside analysis of virtual contrast quality and clinical plausibility. Optionally, we will include a visual Turing-style comparison of images generated by the top-5 ranked models. Respective results will be included in the post-challenge publication.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Data:

[1] L. Garrucho, K. Kushibar, C.-A. Reidel, S. Joshi, R. Osuala, A. Tsirikoglou, et al. A large-scale multicenter breast cancer DCE-MRI benchmark dataset with expert segmentations. *Scientific Data*, 12:453, 2025.

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[2] A. Saha, M. R. Harowicz, L. J. Grimm, J. Weng, E. H. Cain, C. E. Kim, et al. Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance images of breast cancer patients with tumor locations. *The Cancer Imaging Archive*, 2021.

doi:10.7937/TCIA.e3sv-re93.

[3] X. Zhao, Y. Liao, J. Xie, et al. BreastDM: A DCE-MRI dataset for breast tumor image segmentation and classification. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 164:107255, 2023. doi:10.1016/j.combiomed.2023.107255.

[4] G. Müller-Franzes, L. Escudero Sánchez, N. Payne, A. Athanasiou, M. Kalogeropoulos, A. Lopez, et al. A European multi-center breast cancer MRI dataset. *arXiv preprint*, 2025. arXiv:2506.00474.

doi:10.48550/arXiv.2506.00474.

[5] Garrucho, Lidia, et al. "MAMA-MIA Dataset." *Synapse*, 2024, Licensed under a Creative Commons CC-BY-NC License (<https://doi.org/10.7303/syn60868042>)

[6] Li, W., Newitt, et al. I-SPY 2 Breast Dynamic Contrast Enhanced MRI Trial (ISPY2) (Version 1) [Data set] (2022) *The Cancer Imaging Archive* (<https://doi.org/10.7937/TCIA.D8Z0-9T85>)

[7] Newitt, D. C., et al. ACRIN 6698/I-SPY2 Breast DWI [Data set]. (2021) *The Cancer Imaging Archive*. (<https://doi.org/10.7937/TCIA.KK02-6D95>)

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[9] Hylton, Nola M., et al. "Locally advanced breast cancer: MR imaging for prediction of response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy—results from ACRIN 6657/I-SPY TRIAL." *Radiology* 263.3 (2012): 663-672

(<https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.12110748>)

Methods:

[10] R. Osuala, et al. Simulating dynamic tumor contrast enhancement in breast MRI using conditional generative models. *Journal of Medical Imaging*, 12(S2):S22014, 2025. doi:10.1117/1.JMI.12.S2.S22014.

[11] T. Zhang, L. Han, A. D'Angelo, X. et al.. Synthesis of contrast-enhanced breast MRI using T1- and multi-b-value DWI-based hierarchical fusion network with attention mechanism. MICCAI 2023.

doi:10.1007/978-3-031-43990-2_8.

[12] Müller-Franzes, G., Huck, L., Tayebi Arasteh, S., et al. Using machine learning to reduce the need for contrast agents in breast MRI through synthetic images. 2023 *Radiology*, 307(3), e222211.

[13] Lang, D. M., Osuala, R., Spieker, V., Lekadir, K., Braren, R., & Schnabel, J. A. (2025, September). Temporal Neural Cellular Automata: Application to modeling of contrast enhancement in breast MRI. MICCAI 2025. doi:

10.1007/978-3-032-04965-0_57

[14] R. Osuala, D. M. Lang, P. Verma, et al. Towards learning contrast kinetics with multi-condition latent diffusion models. MICCAI 2024. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-72086-4_67

[15] Schreiter, H., Eberle, J., Kapsner, L. A., et al. "Virtual dynamic contrast enhanced breast MRI using 2D U-Net architectures." Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care.

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Metrics:

[17] R. Zhang, P. Isola, A. A. Efros, E. Shechtman, O. Wang. The unreasonable effectiveness of deep features as a perceptual metric. CVPR, 2018. Doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2018.00068

[18] N. Konz, R. Osuala, P. Verma, et al. Fréchet Radiomic Distance (FRD): A versatile metric for comparing medical imaging datasets. arXiv, 2025. arXiv:2412.01496. (Accepted in Medical Image Analysis)

<https://github.com/RichardObi/frd-score>

[19] Wang, Z., Bovik, A.C., Sheikh, H.R. and Simoncelli, E.P., 2004. Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity. *IEEE transactions on image processing*, 13(4), pp.600-612.

Challenges:

[20] MAMA-MIA Consortium. MAMA-MIA Challenge: Advancing generalizability and fairness in breast MRI tumour analysis. MICCAI Challenge, 2025. <https://www.ub.edu/mama-mia/challenge/>

Baselines:

[21] Osuala, R., Skorupko, G., Lazrak, N., et al. medigan: a Python library of pretrained generative models for medical image synthesis. *Journal of Medical Imaging*, 10(6), 061403-061403. 2023. Doi: 10.1117/1.JMI.10.6.061403. (Model 23)

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

The organizers emphasize that this challenge is intended to establish transparent, clinically meaningful evaluation practices for pre-contrast to peak-enhancement translation in breast DCE-MRI. While the official ranking focuses on a limited and clearly defined set of metrics, additional analyses will be performed and reported to support reproducibility, interpretability, and future extension toward regulatory-grade benchmarking.

Furthermore, a Pix2PixHD-based pre-contrast to post-contrast translation model for breast DCE-MRI from [10], as implemented in the medigan framework [21], will be provided as a readily-usable baseline method and model to the participants of the challenge:

<https://medigan.readthedocs.io/en/latest/models.html#pix2pixhd-breast-dcemri>

We will release the baseline's model results for each metric to set a benchmark on validation and test set. These results will be displayed on the leaderboard and the model, as well as its training and inference scripts will be provided on Github for reproducibility.